

Assessment of the Spatial Pattern and Effects of Insurgency in North-Eastern Nigeria

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Abstract: Insurgency activities have continued to ravage the North eastern part of Nigeria since 2009. This resulted in loss of lives and properties. The aim of the study was to examine the spatial spread and effects of insurgency activities in some selected north eastern states of Nigeria. The research identified the insurgency activities in each of the LGAs of the selected states from 2009 to 2017; shows the pattern and trend of the activities; examined the effects of these activities in the study area as well as provide recommendations. The study utilizes both primary and secondary data. Primary data were sourced from questionnaire administration while the secondary data were derived from Armed Conflict Location and Events Data (ACLED), textbooks, journals and relevant security agencies records. The method of analysis used include Geographical Information System (GIS) trend analysis and graphs to show the activities and effects of the insurgency. The result of the analysis showed that the central and eastern part of the area had the highest incidence of insurgency activities within the time frame of the research. The trend analysis revealed an increasing rate of 38 occurrences per year during the period of study. The study therefore recommended that the application of geo-spatial techniques should be incorporated in the fight against insurgency in order to monitor the activities of the insurgency in the study area and Nigeria at large.

Keywords: Spatial Spread, Trend, Effects, Insurgency, North East, Nigeria

INTRODUCTION

One of the major glitches confronting the world today has been the rising cases of insurgency activities. This activity has affected the territorial integrity, sovereignty, socio economic and the political situation of the world. The September 11, 2001 World Trade Center (WTC) bombing in the United States of America by a group known as Al-Qaeda is an example of the first worst act of terror in modern time. Amongst other attacks are the attacks in Great Britain, Spain and other places (Duru & Obonnya, 2010).

Nigeria has its share of attacks by an Islamic extremist group commonly called Boko Haram *Jama'atu Ahlis Sunna Lidda'awati Wal Jihad* which simply means "People Committed to the Propagation of the Prophet's teachings and jihad" now known as the Islamic State of West Africa Province (ISWAP). Its mission and agenda

have been stated to be: "The Eradication of Western Ideology in Nigeria and the realization of Sharia Law in the Country". (Akubor, 2011; Bamigbose, 2011; Nwanegbo & Odigbo, 2013). This deadly group has been involved in attacking international and public buildings, including the United Nations building in Abuja on 26th August, 2011, Army, Police formations, banks, churches, mosques, recreation centers, schools, motor parks, markets and residential areas in Nigeria (Idris, 2013). In spite of the various measures adopted by the Government of the country, the Boko Haram activities did not abate; such efforts would appear to have been frustrated because several attacks occurred after. Such attacks have claimed lives of about 50 students and lecturers of a college in Yobe State and destruction of properties in the institution (Adeniran, *et al.*, 2013; and Chukuma & Philip, 2011). In Benishek alone, the insurgents killed about 161

people, including civilians and soldiers on 17th September, 2013.

The spatial location and controlling of insurgency activities is very complex and requires a systematic and well-designed methodology that will allow a comprehensive analysis of the modes of attack and the degree of vulnerability of specific areas. Advances in the areas of Geographic Information Systems (GIS) and other information technology such as Remote Sensing (RS) have helped in understanding the spread of insurgency, control and prevention. In Iraq, GIS was used to analyze the spread of insurgency activities, and it showed the spatial distribution of where insurgency occurred (Brown et al., 2004). In Pakistan an integration of GPS and GIS were used to identify where insurgency occurred and the impact of insurgency on the environment (Chainey & Ratcliffe, 2005).

The frequency of insurgency activities by Boko Haram sect has caused severe mayhem in North eastern Nigeria through suicide bombing, Kidnapping, attacks on individuals. These various activities have become worrisome to the government because of the inadequacy of information on where and when these activities occur within the shortest time (Abolurin, 2011).

The study of insurgency activities in the North eastern Nigeria have mainly focused on the historical evolution, and the causes of insurgency. Among the studies includes; Awoyemi (2012) who examines the nexus that existed between poverty and the emergence of Boko Haram in Northern Nigeria. Chukwuma and Philip (2014)

provided explanation on unemployment and poverty as a major cause of insurgency activities in the North-eastern region. Eme and Ibietan (2012); Ogochukwu (2013); Oditia and Akan (2014) provided an analysis on the activities of insurgency and how it has affected the socio economic activities in the region. It is therefore necessary to understand the spatial pattern of insurgence activities in order to detect the effects of the activities in the area This will aid in planning the strategies that can be deployed to enhance response time and evacuation of victims in the event of attacks, and also help the government in area of assistance to the people affected by the insurgency activities. Three states were selected in the north eastern Nigeria for this purpose. This was as a result of the frequency of insurgency activities recorded in these states.

Study Area

The study was conducted in Adamawa, Borno, and Yobe state. The area lays between Latitudes 06°00'00"N and 14°00'00"N of the Equator and Longitudes 10°00'00'E and 14°00'00'E of the Greenwich Meridian (see figure 1). It shares international boundaries with three countries, the Niger Republic to the North, the Republic of Chad to the Northeast and Cameroun to the East. It also shares internal boundaries with Jigawa, Bauchi, Gombe and Taraba States to the west (Figure 1.1). The area is made up of 65 Local Government Areas (LGA) and covered a land mass of about 153,317 Km² (Rayar, 1996) and 65 Local Government Areas.

Figure 1: Nigeria showing the Study Area

Source: GIS Cleric (2018) Adopted from National Space and Research Development Agency (NASRDA)

Materials and Methods

Primary data were collected through the use of well-structured questionnaire. Also included are the interviews and observation made during the research. Focus Group Discussion (FGD) were conducted with separate groups of the IDPs to corroborate the findings from the quantitative result. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics such as Mean, standard deviation, and simple percentage in summarizing the data. Also, Pearson Moment Correlation was carried out between the effects to determine their relationships and the correlation matrix was presented and discussed.

Purposive sampling was adopted in the selection of the three states considered based on the frequency of insurgency activities in the areas. The study utilizes documented data from Armed Conflict Location and Events Data (ACLED), Security agencies and newspaper records as well as published studies to investigate the

insurgency activities. The spatial data considered are names of Local Government Areas (LGAs) where insurgency activities occurred and the number recorded within the period considered. These served as the geometry and attribute data.

In the aspect of the effects of insurgency activities in the area considered. A well-structured questionnaire was adopted for this purpose. The target populations for this study were those in the Internal Displaced Camps (IDPs) in the area. Purposive random sampling technique was employed to select the sample size. The sample size for questionnaire administration was determined based on the number of populations in the IDPs. The number of IDPs Camps enumerated was 17 Camps with a total population of 922,174 in the three states that make up the study area (Table 1.1). The level of significance set for the research was at 0.05. A total number of six hundred and thirty-three (633) copies of a structured questionnaire were

administered in the seventeen (17) IDPs Camps in the study area. However, only five hundred and seventy (570) copies were returned adequately completed. This is about 91% of the total respondents. The researcher adopted Naing, et al., (2006) sample size formula in the selection of the sample size, which is shown as follows.

$$\text{Sample size} = \frac{Z^2(1-p)}{d^2}$$

where:

Z = the expected confidence interval (95% adopted and 'Z' table value =1.96)

P= the expected response (50%)

d= the tolerable limits of error (taken to be 5% or 0.05)

Table 1: Sample Size Determination

S/No	States	Number of IDPs Camps	Number of IDPs Camps selected	Population of IDPs	Number of questionnaires administered	Number of questionnaires returned
1	Adamawa	4	2	96,205	160	146
2	Borno	19	10	750,546	301	272
3	Yobe	9	5	75,423	172	152
	Total	32	17	922,174	633	570

Source: Displacement Tracking Matrix XIX (2017)

Result and Discussion

Spatial Pattern of Insurgency Activities

The pattern of insurgency activities in the study area from 2009-2017 is presented in Figure 2. This was achieved using the frequency of insurgency in each of the LGAs in the study area (See Table 2) and the Coefficient of variance of insurgency activities in Table .3. The analysis revealed that Maiduguri experienced the highest incidence of insurgency with 146-413 incidence. Pherhaps this may not be suprising because Maiduguri has been regarded as the birth place of insurgency in the North east (Onuoha, 2012). The high rate of the activities within Maiduguri was as a result of the daily frequencies of insurgency activities earlier recorded from inception of the activities to 2012. At that time, the insurgents were operating as a religion fundamentalist seeking people support and sympathy as well as causing crisis with those that goes against their ideology. Bama, Damboa, Gwoza. Konduga,

Damaturu, Potiskum, and Madagali were next with 83-145 incidence of insurgency.

The high rate of insurgency activities recorded was as a result of the numerous geographical features present in the study area to include the sand dunes, hill shade in areas like Gujba, Gwoza, Madagali, Tarmuwa, Mubi North, and Michika. The insurgency in these areas were also supported by the presence of high elevation from the hill/mountains. Biu recored 47-82 incidence of insurgency activities. Also included in the areas of insurgency activities were those areas located at the North-eastern part of the study area with 17-46 incidence. The analysis further revealed that the pattern of insurgency activities in the study area was at the Eastern and Northeastern part of the area. The concentration of this activities was as a result of the closness of the areas to the international borders between Nigeria and Chad which provided an easy escape route for the insurgents after any incidence, presence of hideouts for insurgents also encouraged the high concentration of

insurgency activities in those areas. This analysis was closely linked to the works of Sadiya et al. (2016); Richard et al. (2011); and Ratcliffe (2000) who pointed out that

insurgency activities tend to be concentrated in an area that provided hiding place for insurgents, and closeness to borders.

Table 2: Frequency of Insurgency Activities in the Study Area (2009-2017)

ADAMAWA STATE			BORNO STATE			YOBE STATE		
S/No	LGA	Frequency	S/No	LGA	Frequency	S/No	LGA	Frequency
1	Fufure	0	1	Abadam	23	1	Bade	3
2	Ganye	2	2	Askira-Uba	45	2	Bursari	0
3	Gombi	15	3	Bama	143	3	Damaturu	72
4	Guyuk	0	4	Bayo	0	4	Fika	5
5	Hong	36	5	Biu	54	5	Fune	6
6	Jada	0	6	Chibok	29	6	Geidam	12
7	Shelleng	1	7	Damboa	108	7	Gujba	36
8	Demsa	2	8	Dikwa	29	8	Gulani	11
9	Madagali	82	9	Gubio	5	9	Jakusko	4
10	Maiha	6	10	Guzamala	21	10	Karasuwa	1
11	Mayo-Belwa	0	11	Gwoza	145	11	Machina	0
12	Michika	23	12	Hawul	35	12	Nangeri	5
13	Mubi-North	16	13	Jere	19	13	Nguru	0
14	Numan	0	14	Kaga	28	14	Potiskum	62
15	Song	2	15	Kala/balge	24	15	Tarmuwa	4
16	Yola-South	20	16	Konduga	76	16	Yunusari	1
17	Mubi-south	2	17	Kukawa	38	17	Yusufari	2
18	Yola-North	6	18	Kwayar-Kusa	1			
19	Girei	3	19	Mafa	42			
20	Toungo	3	20	Magumeri	34			
21	Lamurde	1	21	Maiduguri	413			
			22	Mobbar	26			
			23	Monguno	22			
			24	Marte	24			
			25	Ngala	46			
			26	Ngazai	24			
			27	Shani	7			
	TOTAL	220		TOTAL	1,461		TOTAL	224

Source: ACLED 2019 Version

Table 3: Coefficient of variance of Insurgency Activities

S/No	State	Frequency of insurgency	Average	STDEV	CV
1.	Study Area	1905	211.67	137.54	64.977
2.	Adamawa	220	24.4444	26.42857	108.12
3.	Borno	1461	162.333	100.865	62.13
4.	Yobe	224	24.8889	24.441	98.2

Source: Author’s Computation, 2019

Figure 2: Spatial Pattern of Insurgency Activities in the Study Area (2009-2017)

Source: Author’s Computation, 2019

Temporal (Trend) Pattern of Insurgency Activities

The result of the trend analysis revealed a statistically significant positive trend in insurgency for the period (See Figure 3). This increase was attributed to the hit-and-run methods earlier adopted by the insurgents on those that went against their ideology. The porosity of the borders, presence of hideouts for insurgents has also contributed to this action. However, the declaration of the state of emergency in 2012 provided opportunity for the deployment of more security personnel in the area to discourage insurgency. This action led to the decrease of the activities in 2013 in the area,

but increased in 2014 to early 2015. The rise of the activities was as a result of the pulling out of security agencies from the study area. The insurgency activities decreased from 2015 to 2017 based on the relocation of the service chiefs to the area and also the establishment of more security units to counter insurgency. The result further showed that there was a tendency that the activity might increase in the near future if adequate measures are not taken. The analysis revealed an increasing rate of 38 occurrences per year during the period of study. The R-square statistic shows that the model as fitted explained 58% variability in frequency of insurgency activities in the study area.

Figure 3: Temporal Analysis of Insurgency Activities in the Study Area (2009-2017)

Source: Author’s Computation, 2019

Effects of Insurgency

The effects of insurgency activities are depicted in Figure 4. The loss of lives (23.09%) is the most widespread effects of insurgency. Since the inception of the insurgency activities in 2009 more than three million people had lost their lives (Human Right Watch, 2018). Displacement of people (17.51%) was the second highest effect of insurgency. To support this assertion on 12th October, 2014, the whole of kanumbari village were displaced leaving over 500 people homeless. Similar incidents were experienced in Bama, Damasak, Michika, Baza, Gwoza villages where houses were set ablaze by the insurgents leading to the displacement of over 3,500 people (Internal Displaced Monitoring Center, 2017). Other effects include the destruction of property (15.86%); farm

lands (11.46%); negative effect on the international community’s (11.32%); and lack of trust (11.22%). The result of insurgency activities have destroyed so many property worth millions of naira which include buildings located at FGCC Buni Yadi, College of Agriculture in Yobe and several markets to mention but few. The telecommunication masks in Potiskum, Fune, Bama, Biu, and Yunusafari were also destroyed in 2013. Negative effect on socio-economic activities (9.55%) was the least effect of insurgency in the study area. These results reinforced the findings of Mohammed (2012) and Imam (2004) who reported that the effects of insurgency activities in the North-eastern Nigeria had causes loss of lives, lack of trust, as well as displacement of people.

Figure 4: Effects of Insurgency in the Study Area

Source: Researcher’s field work, 2018

The variation in the effects of insurgency between Adamawa, Borno and Yobe States which formed the area of the study is presented in Table 3. The result showed that there was no statistically significant difference in the magnitude of effects of insurgency activities in the three states of Adamawa, Borno and Yobe, at 95% confidence level. This was because all

the p-values were greater than 0.05. The results suggested that the three states considered in the study experienced the same effects of the insurgency. Although, there were variations among the states, the variations that existed were not significant in the effects of insurgency in the study area (Figure 1.5).

Table 3: Variation in the effects of Insurgency between Adamawa, Borno and Yobe State

		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Loss of lives	Between Groups	1.105	2	.553	1.132	.323
	Within Groups	276.693	567	.488		
	Total	277.798	569			
Destruction of property	Between Groups	7.495	2	3.748	1.050	.351
	Within Groups	2023.094	567	3.568		
	Total	2030.589	569			
Displacement of people	Between Groups	2.722	2	1.361	.361	.697
	Within Groups	2137.777	567	3.770		
	Total	2140.498	569			
Destruction of farmland	Between Groups	2.304	2	1.152	.335	.715
	Within Groups	1947.852	567	3.435		
	Total	1950.156	569			
Negative effects on socioeconomic activities	Between Groups	1.965	2	.983	.491	.612
	Within Groups	1135.340	567	2.002		
	Total	1137.305	569			
Lack of trust	Between Groups	.083	2	.042	.021	.980
	Within Groups	1142.689	567	2.015		
	Total	1142.772	569			
Effects on the international communities	Between Groups	1.509	2	.755	.401	.670
	Within Groups	1066.322	567	1.881		
	Total	1067.832	569			

Source: Researcher's Fieldwork, 2019

Figure 5: Variations in the Effects of Insurgency in the Selected States
Source: Researcher’s Field Work, 2018

Conclusion and Recommendation

This study examined the spatial pattern of insurgency activities in some selected North-eastern state of Nigeria from 2009-2017. The result revealed that insurgency activities were mostly concentrated at the central to the eastern part of the study area. The trend analysis indicated that there was a steady increase of insurgency activities from 2009 to 2015 but decreased after 2015 to 2017. Visualization of the insurgency activities pattern provided a graphical knowledge and understanding of the trend. This knowledge, no doubt, is useful to the government in addressing the issue of insurgency in the north eastern part of Nigeria. The study recommended that the recent advancement in geo-spatial techniques should be an avenue for the Federal Government to invest, train and employ personnel in the utilization of geo-spatial techniques in order to monitor the activities of the insurgency in the study area and Nigeria at large.

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